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Methodological Analysis of Cancer Incidence Trends in Younger Adults: A Critical Note to Garcia-Closas et al. (BMJ Oncol 2026, 10.1136/bmjonc-2025-000966)

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Abstract: After a careful review of the article "Temporal trends in behavioural risk factors for cancers with rising incidence in younger adults" by Garcia-Closas et al., published in *BMJ Oncology* (doi: 10.1136/bmjonc-2025-000966), my analysis of the supplementary data, specifically Table 5, has revealed a methodological issue regarding the interpretation of incidence trends. While the authors present a narrative of an escalating epidemic in younger adults with respect to elderly, the P-value for Time Period Difference reported for the vast majority of cancer sites indicates that the divergence between younger and older cohorts is not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). As the null hypothesis (that the trends in the two age groups are identical) cannot be rejected in these instances, the authors' central conclusion regarding a distinct, age-specific accelerating epidemic appears to be unsupported by the statistical evidence presented in their own materials.

Keywords: *Cancer epidemiology, Incidence trends, Statistical methodology, Garcia-Closas et al. BMJ Oncol, Supplementary data analysis.*

A Note to Garcia-Closas M, et al. Temporal trends in behavioural risk factors for cancers with rising incidence in younger adults: an analysis of population-based data in England. *BMJ Oncol.* 2026

I read with interest the article by Garcia-Closas et al. [1] regarding temporal trends in cancer incidence among younger adults. While the study provides an extensive analysis of population-based data, a detailed examination of the Supplementary Table 5 suggests that the interpretation of an escalating cancer epidemic in younger populations may be methodologically tenuous and clinically questionable.

I wish to highlight the following critical observations (Table 5: Panel B - Men):

- 1. Lack of Statistical Significance in Comparative Trends:** The authors emphasize a marked increase and imply a distinct epidemic among younger adults (20–49 years) compared to older cohorts (50+ years). However, this comparative narrative is unsupported by their own supplementary data. The P-value for Time Period Difference indicates that, for the totality of cancer sites (with the notable exception of Multiple Myeloma), the difference in trends between age groups is not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). In statistical terms, the null hypothesis that the trajectories of the two age groups are identical cannot be rejected. Consequently, framing the rise in incidence as uniquely pronounced or accelerated in the younger cohort, when the statistical divergence between age groups is absent, is a fundamental misinterpretation of comparative trend analysis or an overinterpretation of stochastic fluctuations.
- 2. Deceleration vs. Acceleration:** A comparison between the AAPC (the long-term average) and the Most Recent APC (the latest temporal segment) reveals a consistent pattern of deceleration. In the majority of cancer sites, the Most Recent APC is lower than the AAPC, indicating that the rate of incidence growth is plateauing or slowing in the most recent period (up to 2019). This observation is in contrast with the hypothesis of an accelerating biological epidemic driven by behavioral risk factors, which would typically manifest as a linear or accelerating trend.
- 3. Clinical and Public Health Burden:** The focus on relative percentage changes (AAPC) masks the fundamental clinical reality of the absolute burden of disease. Increases in incidence among the younger population, where baseline rates are often very low, translate into a negligible absolute increase in the number of cases. Conversely, even small relative increases in the older population (where baseline rates are high) represent a significantly larger absolute number of patients requiring clinical management. Prioritizing relative trends in low-incidence groups over absolute case

volume in high-incidence groups risks misdirecting public health resources and policy priorities.

4. **Unstable Behavioral Risk Factor Trends:** The temporal heterogeneity observed, particularly the tendency toward stabilization or decline in the older cohort, seems to suggest that the observed rise in incidence is driven by period effects, such as changes in diagnostic practices or screening intensity, rather than a fundamental shift in etiological risk factors.
5. **Panel A (Women) and Heterogeneity of Trends:** An analysis of the data for women reveals substantial heterogeneity that undermines the concept of a uniform epidemic. While certain sites show consistent growth, others, most notably liver cancer, exhibit a striking reversal of trends in the most recent period. Aggregating these diverse trajectories into a singular conclusion of an accelerating epidemic is methodologically confounding and obscures the fact that, for the majority of sites, the growth phase has either stabilized or reversed.

In conclusion, the data presented in the supplementary material suggest that the narrative of a distinct and accelerating cancer epidemic among younger adults requires significant qualification. We kindly ask the authors to reconsider their conclusions in light of the clinical burden and the absence of statistical divergence between age groups.

Reference

Garcia-Closas M, et al. Temporal trends in behavioural risk factors for cancers in young adults. *BMJ Oncol.* 2026;5:e000966. doi: 10.1136/bmjonc-2025-000966

Competing Interest: None to declare.

Use of AI: The author declares no use of AI in support to this note.